

**Histological examinations of the mycelium and spores of taro leaf blight pathogen
(*Phytophthora colocasiae* Racib.)**

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Abstract

Leaf blight and tuber rot are the main pathological disease constraints in taro (*Colocasia esculenta* L.), and are the major production constraints. The oomycete *Phytophthora colocasiae* (*P. colocasiae*), which is the causative agent, is an aerial pathogen with a filamentous structure composed of hyphae. The latter is an indispensable component of both the biological and infectious cycles. The aim of this study was to investigate the different stages of mycelium formation and the resulting vegetative structures. For this purpose, the histological sections were prepared from the mycelium obtained by culturing an isolate of the pathogen in liquid medium. The results obtained show that the mycelium is formed from a thallus, which gradually lengthens the branches and, intertwines and forms a dense mycelial network. Subsequently, the mycelium differentiates into sporangiosphores, which carry sporangia that are gradually detached from their branches. The resulting mycelia differentiated into chlamydopsoria. We also noted the presence of vegetative structures of various shapes and sizes, which approach each other and merge with each other. This is new in the biology of *Phytophthora colocasiae* and the observed fusion of spores can explain the genetic diversity observed within the species.

Key-words: Taro leaf blight, *Phytophthora colocasiae*, mycelium, sporangiosphores, sporangia, chlamydospores, spores.

Introduction

Taro is grown worldwide, particularly in Africa, China, the United States and India [1]. It is commonly used as a staple food [2] and remains one of the oldest cultivated tuber plants in the Araceae family [3]. In Cameroon, taro is cultivated in all regions for its leaves and tubers [4]. Taro contains a high content of carbohydrates, minerals, proteins, and vitamins [5]. In addition to their nutritional properties, taro tubers contain valuable bioactive molecules that are effective against cancer and cancer-related risk factors, such as carcinogens and, several pathophysiological conditions, including oxidative stress and inflammation, while controlling dysfunction and stimulating the immunological response [6]. These health and nutritional benefits are valuable characteristics of taro owing to their dietary benefits.

However, in Cameroon, taro production is limited by many factors including diseases such as taro leaf blight (*Phytophthora colocasiae* Racib.). The disease affects leaves and tubers, resulting in extensive damage to the plant [7, 8] causing a potential yield loss of up to 100 %

[8]. The disease is still not well managed owing to the complex life cycle of the pathogen. The life cycle of *P. colocasiae*, which is an oomycete, is based on growth characteristics such as semi-biotrophic and necrotrophic parasitic stages [9]. This requires additional knowledge of pathogen biology. However, several studies have established the crucial role of the mycelia form of the pathogen in nutrition, growth as well as in reproduction and infection [10, 11]. In addition, the mycelium of *P. colocasiae* enters harvested tubers and causes heavy post-harvest losses [12]. Thus, a good understanding of the mechanisms leading to the formation of mycelia and spores could provide useful information, which would lead to the utilization of new control methods, such as blocking the early stages of the pathogen cycle. Therefore, this preliminary study was carried out with the aim of studying the different stages of the mycelial formation and spores of *P. colocasiae*.

Material and method

Identification of the botanical sample

The biological material was collected and analysed in accordance with the national requirements mentioned in the Order N° 0072/MINADER/SG/DRCQ/SDRSQV of 22 April 2019, establishing procedures for the recognition of species and varieties. The botanical sample was identified and confirmed at the National Herbarium of Cameroon.

Isolation and identification of the pathogen

The method described in [13] was used to obtain *P. colocasiae* strain used in this study. In fact, fragmented tissue of 5 to 10 mm² was obtained from the margins of lesions presented on the leaves of *Colocasia esculenta*, showing the typical symptoms of taro leaf blight: initial infection from water-soaked lesions that rapidly expand to form circular, zonate, and brown spots. When the weather becomes dry, the lesions becomes brown, and the edges are dark brown or black. White and powdery masses of spores can be produced on these blights [11]. These tissues were then cut into small fragments of 2 mm², and disinfected using a 5% sodium hypochlorite solution for 2 min. After rinsing three times in a row with sterile distilled water, the fragments were dried on hydrophilic paper and placed in Petri dishes containing the V8-agar medium. This medium, recommended by [14] for the cultivation of *P. colocasiae* because it provides good isolation, growth, and sporulation of the pathogen, has been supplemented with penicillin (250 mg/L), ampicillin (250 mg/L), and nystatin (20 mg/L) [15]. After three days of incubation at 21°C, the emerging mycelium was transferred onto sterilized Potato Dextrose

Agar medium (PDA; 250 g/L potato, 20 g/L dextrose, and 20 g/L agar) to obtain a pure culture [16]. The procedure was repeated several times. The pathogen was identified by examining its microscopic and macroscopic patterns [17].

Pathogenicity test

A pathogenicity test was performed using the floating leaf disc method [18]. Leaf discs approximately 80 mm in diameter were obtained from healthy *Colocasiae esculenta* leaves without any symptoms of leaf blight. They were introduced into 90 mm diameter glass Petri dishes containing 5 mL of sterile distilled water and sterile blotting paper. A mycelium fragment of 2 to 3 mm² collected from the growth margins of a 7 day-old pure culture of *P. colocasiae* was deposited on the leaf disc. Leaf pieces with mycelia-free agar fragments served as controls (figure 1 A). The plates were incubated in the dark at 21°C for 7 days [18]. The leaf discs were observed daily to observe the onset of symptoms. The pathogen was re-isolated from the observed lesions according to Koch's postulate [17].

Culture in liquid medium

Small fragments of actively growing pure cultures of *P. colocasiae* strain were introduced into an Erlenmeyer flask (250 mL) containing 100 mL of autoclaved V8 broth medium to obtain more free biomass of pathogen in the substrate. The cultures were then placed on a rotary shaker at 50 rpm and incubated at an ambient temperature (21±1°C). After 15 days of incubation, mycelia were harvested by filtration through sterile cheesecloth, blotted dry with sterile paper towels, and prepared for histological examination [19].

Histological examinations of the mycelium of *P. colocasiae*

The mycelia obtained were handled gently to avoid any trauma to the sample. It was cut transversely into sections of 1mm². The cut was made continuously from the peripheral regions towards the center of growth of the mycelial mass to analyze the entire surface area. The resulting sections were labeled and immediately fixed in 10% formalin solution [20].

The samples were then placed in a cassette and processed according to routine histological technique and staining with hematoxylin-eosin [20]. For this purpose, they were first dehydrated by successive passages at 80° alcohol baths of increasing concentrations at room temperature (22 ± 1 °C) for 1h, followed by two successive baths of 95° alcohol for 2 h each. The sample was then, finalized by successively passing it through two baths of 100° alcohol for 2h for each passage [20]. The dehydrated sections were then treated successively in three baths

of xylene at room temperature for 1 h for the first bath and 2 h for the second and third baths. This was followed by transferring the samples from xylene to paraffin in an oven at 58°C through two successive baths of paraffin for 2h each. After 4 h of inclusion, embedding was carried out using a tissue-embedding center and molds to obtain blocks on the corresponding cassettes. After cooling using a cooling plate at – 10°C for 10 min, hard blocks were obtained, inside which sample sections were included [20].

Microtomy and staining

The paraffin block was introduced in a manual microtome, which was used to produce mycelia sections of 4 µm thick. The sections obtained were spread on glass slides with ground edges containing a solution of glycerinated albumin as an adhesive (50 mL of fresh egg white, 50 mL of glycerol and 1 mL of sodium salicylate) diluted to 1:20. The glass slides were subsequently placed in a 45°C water bath for 5s to straighten the sections. After drying, the slides were stained with hematoxylin-eosin [21] and examined using a Leica EZ4W microscope coupled with a Leica ICC50 W Camera manufactured by Leica Microsystems.

Result and discussion

Identification of the botanical sample

The botanical sample was identified and confirmed at the National Herbarium of Cameroon by Mr. NGANSOP T. Eric, Botanist, Systematist and Taxonomist, as *Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schott (Araceae) in comparison with the original material of the National Herbarium N° 42359/HNC collected by Westphal under N° 10085.

Pathogen isolation, pathogenicity test and mycelium production

Leaves showing typical symptoms of taro leaf blight were grown on V8 solid medium and the pathogen was isolated after three days. By comparing its morphological characteristics with the existing data on *Phytophthora*, it was clearly identified as *P. colocasia*. This result was confirmed by the pathogenicity test, which showed that the isolate caused the typical necrosis of taro late blight from the third day after inoculation (figure 1B). Leaf piece disks with mycelia-free agar after three days served as controls (figure 1A). The inoculation points initially appeared as water-soaked lesions, which turned brown as the disease progressed.

Figure 1: Leaf piece disk with mycelia-free agar after 3 days serve as control (A), late blight symptoms on taro leaf disk, 3 days after inoculation (B).

The pathogen was reisolated from these lesions according to Koch's postulates. [22] reported similar features in a study on the diversity of *P. colocasia* isolates in India. In liquid medium, pure cultures of the pathogen produced profuse mycelia after 15 days of cultivation (figure 2B), with visible quantities already getting on the fifth day (figure 2A). The mycelial mass was uniform and milky white, and no mycelial growth was observed in the control test (figure 2C).

Figure 2: Pure culture of *P. colocasiae* produce profuse mycelium with visible quantity already getting on the fifth day on autoclaved V8 broth medium (A), pure culture of the pathogen after fifteen days of cultivation on autoclaved V8 broth medium (B) and control test shows the absence of mycelia growth on autoclaved V8 broth medium (C).

Histology

Many filamentous organisms, such as oomycetes, develop from isolated cells into branched filaments. Thallus development depends on hyphal elongation, branching patterns, and differentiation [23]. *P. colocasiae* mycelium invades harvested tubers and causes severe post-harvest losses [12]. It is involved in reproduction, nutrition, differentiation and host infection [11]. Therefore, it is logical to trace the different stages of mycelium formation. From this perspective, we used histological techniques to obtain information on the growth and differentiation of *P. colocasiae* hyphae. The results identified three types of hyphae: the lateral hyphae (figure 3A), first appearing from mycelia implants, the conductive hyphae (figure 3B) and intermediate filaments (figure 3C). These findings are in agreement with earlier descriptions by [24], who categorized different types of vegetative hyphae as conducting filaments (leading hyphae), lateral filaments (wandering and floundering hyphae), and intermediate filaments (submarginal and starving hyphae).

Figure 3: Stages of the mycelium development in *P. colocasiae* by apical elongation and branching of the hyphae. Lateral hyphae (A), conductive hyphae (B), intermediate hyphae (C) and intermingled hyphae (D), X 1000.

As a result, during the early hours of thallus' growth, only lateral hyphae were created. Later, as the floundering elements remained the same morphologically, the growing elements of the thallus' margin increased in size and produced larger articles. Ultimately, the rate of thallus elongation reaches a maximum, which is attained when all front' filaments are converted. The new hyphae that emerged as far as the growing margin were collectively referred to as conductors. They are molded by the rapid advancement of the substrate and the long distance transport of cellular materials. Overall, the hyphae could have evolved through progressive lengthening of the rhizoids that linked the substrate of the first fungus [25, 26]. As they mature, they maximize the efficiency of their foraging and minimize competition for nutrients through a pattern of growth that is similar to the fractal [27, 28].

Additionally, the function of the lateral hyphae is crucial, as they are the origin of the vegetative structures of conservation. These structures are capable of producing hyphae, but they also ensure the supply of all other mycelia forms via their capacity to penetrate the substrate. In addition, our observations suggest that the hyphae in extension appeared to have, at some points, a spherical region that was probably the apical body (figure 4). The apical region at the top of the hypha is the area of growth extension of mycelium [23]. It is positioned in the middle when the hyphae continue to grow in the same direction, but a change in the direction of growth is preceded by displacement of the apical body to the side of the hypha's end, followed by its return to the central position [29]. Similarly, a new branch is preceded by the creation of a new apical body in the space, whereas growth cessation is signaled by the loss of the apical body. One of the primary structures in the growth of hypha is the apical body, which functions as a center for the distribution of vesicles that carry cell wall components and other substances to the tip of the hypha [29]. Furthermore, the hypothesis of locomotor activity at the apical body level can be proposed. Indeed, research on apical growth dynamics suggests that the cytoskeleton, by interacting with motor proteins and calcium, plays a central role in apical development. This end can be promoted by actin polymerization; the cytoplasm flows towards the end with the help of motor proteins that interact with the components of the cytoskeleton [23]. These observations, as well as previous observations, suggest hyphal growth. Indeed, the hyphal growth illustrated in figure 3 can be summarized as follows: the mycelium is formed from a thallus, which gradually elongates and transforms to produce lateral and conductive hyphal forms.

Figure 4: Extension of the hyphae from the apical body (arrow), X 1000.

These branches actively branch out in the submarginal region, giving rise to branches that can grow parallel to the axis and retain conductive morphology, or diverge to obtain lateral aspect and behavior. The former assembles to form a conductive morphology, whereas the latter vegetates in an environment where they develop a lateral system embedded in the substrate. This leads to interwoven structures that form a dense network of hyphae (figure 3D). These results are in accordance with the information that mycelium formation is dependent on the network of cell polarity [30], exo and endocytic machinery, long-range vesicle transport, and cell wall assembly and branching points [31]. However, the transition from one type of mycelium to another is typically gradual. This necessarily implies intermediate or transitional forms, starting from the side-type morphologies and, evolving into conductive-type morphologies, or vice versa.

Therefore, we can observe that *P. colocasiae* grows as the end of hyphae elongates. This observation is consistent with the work done by [23], who showed that fungi are characterized by apical growth of mycelia from the apex to the oldest regions. They resemble oomycetes because of their similar feeding habits and mycelial systems [32]. This growth can be explained on several levels. First, *P. colocasiae* is a non-photosynthetic oomycete with a heterotrophic metabolism. Its basic cell unit is the mycelium, which has an absorptive mode of nutrition [33]. Therefore, it absorbs nutrients present in the environment, which are useful for its growth.

Mycelial growth seems to be one of the extraordinary activities at the top of the hyphae, where there are numerous vesicles that transport lysis and biosynthetic enzymes at high speed to the plasma membrane. *P. colocasiae* is known to be a potential producer of pectin- and cellulose-degrading enzymes that play key roles in pathogenesis [34]. As vesicles fuse with the plasma membrane, they also contribute, to the expansion of the plasma membrane, along with their own membrane components. Furthermore, the growth of the mycelium involves the extension of the wall and, thus, the biosynthesis of its components. A major enzyme involved in pathogen wall growth is glucan synthase that catalyzes the synthesis of β -1,3glucans [23] the major structural compounds of *P. colocasiae* according to [35]. This enzyme is expected to reach vesicles and insert into the plasma membrane of the apex. Finally, wall lysis enzymes also appear to be involved in mycelial branching, as new peaks are generated from the existing mature hyphal wall [23].

According to the growth of the mycelium, the obtained results show that the mycelium is gradually differentiated by the introduction of an axis, followed by rapid elongation, finally leading to the formation of sporangiophores, which carry sporangia at their ends (figure 5). These observations are supported by the biology of *Phytophthora* [11]. This author was able to show that, during its biological cycle, the emerging mycelium of *Phytophthora* is transformed into the sporangiophore through which the sporangium is formed. For [36], it is the cycle of asexual reproduction by which *Phytophthora* spreads by forming asexual propagation organs called sporangia, which can release spores. For [37], sporangium development is a regular, multi-stage process. Shaft formation is followed by rapid elongation in stage 1, growth stops and sporangia differentiate in stage 2. Stage 3 corresponds to the end of this phase, and in stage 4, elongation continues at the level of the subsporangial region. In contrast, stage 5 is marked by the cessation of growth and gradual detachment of the sporangium.

Once the sporangium separated from the branches of the sporangiophores, the resulting hyphae differentiated into two types of chlamydospores. Some were in the middle of the mycelium, and some were at the end (figure 5F). Referring to the work of [38], it is probably intercalary chlamydospore for the anterior chlamydospore and terminal chlamydospore for the latter. One of the most likely explanations for the timing of these vegetative structures is that when nutrients provided by the substrate are abundant, they are exploited by pathogens for vigorous vegetative growth. When they are depleted, vegetative growth stops and pathogens must survive by spreading or entering a latent state. For *P. colocasiae*, dispersal and dormancy are carried out by differentiated spores, such as terminal and intercalary chlamydospores [16].

Figure 5: Differentiation of mycelium into sporangiospores and spores. Progressive formation of the sporangiospore (A, B and C), detachment of sporangia (D and E), formation of chlamydospores (F), X1000.

Speaking precisely of spores, this histological study allows us to note that after its hyphae development and differentiation into sporangia and chlamydo spores; *P. colocasiae* produces many spherical vegetative structures, ovoid and piriform characterized by the absence of one or more papillae and the presence of one or more papillae (figures 6). These vegetative structures are likely spores formed when adverse conditions arise for the pathogen. Considered as resistant structures, they are also the structures through which vegetative reproduction is carried out in *Phytophthora* species [39]. Similar morphologies in figures 6 H, L and P were obtained by pairing compatible mating patterns of *P. colocasiae* and *Phytophthora nicotianae* [40]. In addition, because no germination was observed, one would think that these spores were in a dormant state. This state is defined as the period from the end of sporulation to the beginning of germination and is characterized primarily by reduced metabolic activity. These spores were observed after the formation of mycelia and, therefore, after a drastic reduction in environmental nutrients. An exogenous dormant state may be due to the absence of a favorable environment for growth. Endogenous dormancy depends on the structural or metabolic features of spores [23].

In contrast, sporocysts showing a potential germinal filament producing a thallus were observed at their ends, as illustrated in figure 6 G showing the initiation of germination. This mode of germination in *P. colocasiae* corresponds to direct germination [41]. We also observed spherical spores surrounded by small vegetative structures (figure 6 C, D, M, O, Q, B', C', D', and F'). The nature of spores observed according to whether they are of asexual or sexual origin can be widely discussed. Indeed, species of the genus *Phytophthora* can exhibit both sexual and asexual cycles [36]. However, it is important to clarify that *P. colocasiae* is a heterozygous oomycete that requires the presence of two opposite mating types for the production of oospores [42].

Figure 6: Morphology of the spores formed after differentiation of the mycelium. Spores of spherical morphology with papilla (A, C, D, E, G, I, M, O, R, T, V, B', D' and F'), spore with spherical morphology without papilla (B, N and E'), spores of ovoid morphology with papilla (F, H, K, L, P, Q, S, U, W, X, Z, A' and C'), spore of ovoid morphology without papilla (Y), spores of piriform morphology with papilla (J), X 1000.

Since these spores are obtained from pure culture, the hypothesis that they are oospores is unlikely because, owing to their heterothallic nature, they do not carry all the genetic material required for sexual development in the nucleus. In Revenge, a likely situation was reported in Taiwan, where isolates of *P. colocasiae* could be transformed into different mating patterns A1, A2 and asexual offspring [17]; illustrates that a change in mating type can occur in a single culture during asexual growth. At the same time, according to a previous study [43], *P. colocasiae*, although heterozygous, is capable of producing oogonia in pure culture. The presence of oospores, which are sexual spores, indicates sexual reproduction, which ensures natural selection and adaptation of the organism to environmental conditions by allowing beneficial mutations [44]. This suggests that they are induced by *P. colocasiae* to survive the substrate reduction in the environment. Sexual reproduction introduces a form of long-lived inoculum owing to the longevity and durability of the oospores, which can survive for a long time under a variety of conditions [40]. Similar information was also reported by [17], owing to the abundant presence of oospores in infected taro tissues, suggesting that these spores serve as survival structures. Although oospores have been established as resistant structures in homothallic *Phytophthora* [45], oospores of heterothallic *Phytophthora* are rare in naturally infected soils [46]. This rarity could be explained by the fact that it is difficult for both mating types of *Phytophthora* to occur in the same host tissue, as most studies on mating distribution have shown only the presence of type A1 or A2 [47]. Furthermore, according to the life cycle of *P. colocasiae* elucidated in [11], when environmental conditions are saturated with water, these oospores can germinate at a low frequency and form sporangia. These sporangia can release zoospores depending on the temperature and humidity. At the same time, [48] believe that oospores are dormant, resistant, thick-walled spores that can germinate directly to produce mycelia or sporangia.

Histological analyses also made it possible to illustrate the interaction between numerous spores of spherical, pyriform, ovoid shapes, and variable sizes, characterized by the absence or presence of papillae. These spores tended to approach each other (figure 7A), stick to each other (figure 7B) and merge together (figure 7C).

Figure 7A: Some spores move closer to each other, X 1000.

The proximity of spores alludes to tropism, which is a directional or locomotor response induced by physical or chemical agents. Thus, evidence for hormone production by *P. colocasiae* and its involvement in sexual reproduction has been provided by [49]. In addition to the assembly of mycelia during sexual reproduction by hormonal mechanisms [50] or even electrical or chemical impulses that can partially rupture the membrane of zoospores and attract them. According to [51], the phytol-synthesized hormone α_2 is used by *Phytophthora* to promote sexual reproduction.

Figure 7B: Images showing the spores sticking together, X 1000.

The result is spore fusion, which closely resembles the steps of plasmogamy involving the union of two protoplasts, whereby karyogamy contributing to nuclear fusion would take place in some species [23]. However, sexual mechanisms are also known to occur in *P. colocasiae*. In antheridium and oogonia, meiotic division of the diploid genome occurs and a haploid nucleus is formed. An antheridial nucleus is transferred into the oogonium through a fertilization tube and fuses with the nucleus of the oogonium. This results in a sexual spore known as an oospore [12]. These evoked mechanisms, coupled with the fact that we are in a pure culture, add to the heterothallic character of *P. colocasiae*, which suggests somatic fusion. This hypothesis is supported by the work done by [36], who was able to highlight cases of somatic hybridization by fusing compatible spores and hyphae in oomycetes. In the same opinion, some authors [52, 53] have highlighted cases of vegetative fusion in *Phytophthora*. Similar to [44], nutrient restriction stimulates pheromone production and, induces cell fusion, and as a result, the dikaryon undergoes filamentous transformation. The possibility of a parasexual mechanism borrowing the plasmogamy stage can also be evoked considering the complexity of this heterothallic and diploid oomycete, as well as that of the genus *Phytophthora*, which is in perpetual motion. Likewise, the evolutionary history of species is elusive and their boundaries are still uncertain [54].

Evidence of mitotic recombination in *Phytophthora* species has been reported [55-57] as suggested by [58] following, a study that *P. colocasiae* would have a recombinant mode of reproduction. Theoretically, these recombinations events could result from clonal, mitotic, or sexual recombination in the form of homologous recombination [59].

Overall, regardless of the nature of the fusion observed, it will have a great impact on recombination and the formation of new genotypes, allowing *P. colocasiae* to easily adapt to various environmental conditions and simultaneously induce genetic variation. This analysis is consistent with the conclusion reached after a study stipulating that isolated strains of *P. colocasiae* show a high degree of genetic variability regardless of geographical origin [58]. Using *Bdelloid rotifers* as eukaryotic model organisms, instances of cross-species and species-specific horizontal gene transfers have been demonstrated [60].

Figure 7C: Image showing the exchange of cytoplasm between spores following their attachment (arrow) X 1000.

In addition to sexual reproduction, genetic variation observed in populations can be obtained by asexual mechanisms such as heterokaryosis, parasexuality, and somatic inheritance, which involve cytoplasmic mixing [23].

Another consequence of this sporadic fusion is an increase in the ploidy of the resulting unit [61]. Because the experiments were conducted in pure cultures, our arguments are more inclined towards self-polyploidy. This is the case with *Phytophthora porri*, where complete genome duplication occurs, resulting autopolyploidy [59]. Therefore, *P. colocasiae* as an oomycete is diploid in the vegetative state [33], so the fusion of two diploid spores could be a potential source of polyploidy. Recent work has identified strains of *P. colocasiae* with diploid, triploid, tetraploid, and higher ploidy genomes; this polyploidy was distributed within and among populations [63]. This is also the case for *Phytophthora alni*, which is considered hybrid that has undergone allopolyploid-type polyploidization according to the work of [52, 53]. According to [59], the occurrence of DNA content variation and polyploidization in *Phytophthora* species is related to hybridization events. In addition, during this fusion, other mechanisms such as translocations, deletions, and duplications of chromosomes may occur and may be a possible means of genetic variation [58]. Interspecific hybridization and polyploidization are two related phenomena in *Phytophthora*, which may play an important and ongoing role in the evolution process of this genus [59].

Although *P. colocasiae* has been shown to reproduce sexually in the laboratory, asexual reproduction is more important [59]. According to [63], asexual species can be formed under the influence of several factors through hybridization. In addition, sexual reproduction between mating patterns A1 and A2 produces a longer-lived inoculum because of the longevity and durability of the oospores [40]. On the other hand, if sexually produced spores become less important for dissemination and conservation, then the selective pressure to maintain sexual reproduction will be low, and the relevant pathogen may become asexual. Furthermore, when the spores produced are important for the survival of the species, strong selection for self-sterility takes place; therefore, the nature of the spores produced is of great importance [23].

The presence of both mycelia and the sporadic vegetative form of *P. colocasiae* in this study confirms its dimorphic character. It is a specific form of differentiation, consisting of the pathogen changing from the mycelium to the unicellular or sporadic stage in response to changing environmental conditions [23]. This result is explained in the work of [11] on the life cycle of *Phytophthora*, in which the mycelium differentiates into sporangiophores, bearing the

sporangium at the tip. However according to [64], which showed that *P. colocasiae* is a heterogeneous species that produces, sporangiophores, sporangia, and zoospores.

This study made it possible to elucidate, through histology, the morphological complexity of *P. colocasiae*, which can appear both in mycelia and sporadically. Additionally, it showed the interaction between the pathogen spores, which resulted in fusion and mixing of the cytoplasm. This mixture of cytoplasm could create new morphotypes and cause a reorganization of the resulting unit, leading to genetic variability, polymorphism, appearance of more virulent strains, and formation of new taxa and new species, given the high evolutionary potential of the *Phytophthora* species. In this vein, a re-evaluation of all *Phytophthora meadii* and *P. colocasiae* ITS sequence data identified seven additional putative new species [65]. These results support the view that many more *Phytophthora* species need to be discovered. Many new taxa and species have been identified from *Phytophthora* [66].

Conclusion

The microscopic anatomy of the mycelium of *P. colocasiae* showed apical and progressive growth of hyphae, giving rise to lateral buds. These have undergone morphological changes leading to differentiated structures, such as sporangiophores, sporangia, and chlamydospores. The nature of the spores observed and the phenomenon of somatic fusion raise questions about cell differentiation and reproduction in *P. colocasiae*. Thus, a good understanding of the biology of the mycelial form of *P. colocasiae*, as well as the determinism of the different stages of differentiation and reproduction, could be considered as an avenue in the management of taro late blight.

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Ethical statement

The biological material was collected and analysed in accordance with the national requirements mentioned in the Order N° 0072/MINADER/SG/DRCQ/SDRSQV of 22 April 2019, establishing procedures for the recognition of species and varieties. The botanical sample was identified and confirmed at the National Herbarium of Cameroon by Mr. NGANSOP T. Eric, Botanist, Systematist and Taxonomist, as *Colocasiae esculenta* (L.) schott (Araceae) in comparison with the original material of the National Herbarium N° 42359/HNC collected by Westphal under N° 10085.

Author's contribution

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Data availability statement

The data that support this study are openly available in ‘‘Zenodo’’

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